

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON EDUCATIONAL SETUPS IN THE ACADEMIC SKILL DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITIES

Bhola Vishwakarma

Research Scholar (Ph.D), Jagdishprasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University, Rajasthan.

Abstract

In India, the concept of Inclusive Education has not yet been linked to a broader discussion of pedagogy and quality education. Any broad reform in education cannot be implemented without taking the inclusion of learners with special education need into consideration. It is a challenging task for parent, teacher and administrator to meet the educational need of children with intellectual disability. Early screening, identification and properly intervention of children with intellectual disability is more challenging issue for the society which may adversely affects the academic development of the child. There are several educational setups like special, integrated and inclusive schools for children with intellectual disability but this is the question mark which type of educational service is more beneficial for that children, because of all special education need children has been come under inclusive education and only intellectually disabled children can't learn higher education like other disabled person. So, this study fulfills the goal of education of children with intellectual disabilities.

Key Words: *Special, Integrated, Inclusive, Schools, Academic Development, Intellectually Disabled.*

Introduction

Special schools for children with visual impairment, hearing impairment, and locomotor disabilities are streamlined to follow a curriculum that is almost inline with the general education curriculum. In 1947, India had a total of 32 such schools for the blind, 30 for the deaf, and three for the mentally retarded. The number of such schools increased to around 3000 by the year 2000. In other words, it has parallel but separate policies on segregation and integration. The plus and minus curriculum and the adaptation of instructional methodologies are followed where necessary. Children with mental retardation on the other hand require a specialised curriculum to meet their specific educational needs.

In the 1970s, the government launched the Centrally Sponsored Scheme of Integrated Education for Disabled Children (IEDC). The objective was to integrate children with disabilities in the general community at all levels as equal partners to prepare them for normal development and to enable them to face life with courage and confidence. The scheme aimed at providing educational opportunities to learners with disabilities in regular schools, and to facilitate their achievement and retention.

Inclusion means full inclusion of children with diverse abilities in all aspects of schooling that other children are able to access and enjoy. It involves regular schools and classrooms genuinely adapting and changing to meet the needs of all children, as well as celebrating the valuing differences. This definition does not imply that children with diverse abilities will not receive specialized assistance or teaching outside of the classrooms when required, but rather that this is just one of many options that are available to, and infect required of all children.

Review

Florian (2008) examined the relationships between 'special' and 'inclusive' education. She explores the implications of the use of the concept of special needs, especially in relation to attempts to implement inclusion in practice and she notes the tensions that arise from these relationships. **Brahm (2008)** examines the roles that special schools can play within inclusive educational system also he summarises findings on teachers' attitudes towards this crucial "dilemma of difference" from three countries and argues that it is time to develop more sophisticated ways of thinking about provision. Rather than insisting on locating "mainstream" and "special" at opposite ends of a one-dimensional placement continuum. **Nugent (2007)** compares Inclusive and segregated Settings for children with Dyslexia. This study evaluates and compares special educational services for children with dyslexia in three different settings: special schools, reading units and mainstream resource provision. They was noted that, while parents expressed a preference for inclusive services in theory, in reality, once provided with services, parents were actually more satisfied with specialist segregated services. **Mani & Manivannan (2004)** highlights that a single model educational programme is not suitable for all children with learning disabilities living in different areas. The service delivery model is to be based on need and accessibility. **Punani (1997)** presents a comparative evaluation of the effectiveness of various modes of education of visually impaired children. Findings reveal that integrated education was the most effective with respect to coverage of special groups such as girls, younger children, congenitally visually impaired children and those coming from traditionally less educated families. **Conrad & Kenneth (1980)** selected fifty primary research studies of special versus regular class placement were selected for use in a meta-analysis. Special classes were found to be significantly inferior to regular class placement for students with below average IQs, and significantly superior to regular classes for behaviorally disordered, emotionally disturbed, and learning-disabled children.

Need of the Study

Each of the educational setups is equally important, yet there seems to exist significant difference in their mode of delivering the activity. One should critically analyze the various factors of each of these educational setups and then place the child with their need and requirement. Since decision makers (Parents, Teachers & Para-professionals) in the education of children with intellectual disabilities face contradictory opinions.

Objectives

1. To compare the educational setups in the academic skill development of boys with intellectual disabilities.
2. To compare the educational setups in the academic skill development of girls with intellectual disabilities.
3. To compare the academic skill development of boys and girls with intellectual disabilities in different educational setups.

Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant difference among the educational setups in the academic skill development of boys with intellectually disabled.

Ho2: There is no significant difference among the educational setups in the academic skill development of girls with intellectually disabled.

Ho3: There is no significant difference in the academic skill development of boys and girls with intellectually disabled in different educational setups.

Methodology

The present study aims at comparing the different educational setups in providing academic skill development for children with intellectually disabled. For the conduct of the present study 3 different types of school namely special, integrated and inclusive school were selected from the population. The samples were selected from 3 special schools, 2 integrated schools and 4 inclusive schools from the district of Coimbatore. The present study focuses on the academic skill development for children intellectually disabled. Hence the investigator selected purposive sampling technique for the selection of sample.

Variables: The variables selected for the present study are.

Independent Variables

1. Type of schools - Special, Integrated, Inclusive.
2. Gender - Male, Female.

Dependent Variables - Academic skills

Inclusion Criteria

- a) Children studying in special, integrated & Inclusive schools.
- b) Children with Intellectual Disabled.
- c) Children within age range of 6-11 years.
- d) Children of either gender.

Selection of the Tool

The appropriate check list was used for this research study. The checklists consist of a list of items with a place to check or to mark 'Yes' or 'No'. The list of items in the checklist may be continuous or divided into groups of related items. The checklist consisted of 40 items to assess the academic performance of the respondent. These 40 items were chosen from the standardized Functional Assessment Checklist Programming (FACP) tool at primary-I level from the academic domain developed by National Institute for the Mentally Handicapped. To assess the items of the tools, the investigator prepared and also collected appropriate materials to check the performance of the sample. Through keen observation of the performance of the sample, the investigator made an assessment in the tool. Thus the data was collected for the study.

Data Analysis Procedure

The collected data was tabulated and consolidated for further statistical treatment. The grouped data was then subjected to quantitative analysis, using ANOVA and t-test.

Ho1: There is no significant difference among the educational setups in the academic skill development of boys with intellectually disabled.

Table 1: Anova Test for Comparing Educational Setups in the Academic Skills Development of the Subject of the Boys Sample

Different Setups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Special School	6	22.3333	13.3666
Integrated School	6	31.3333	5.7155
Inclusive School	5	25.4000	9.3968
Total	17	26.4118	10.1861

ANOVA for Able to do Score

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	250.251	2	125.125	1.242	Ns
Within Groups	1409.867	14	100.705		
Total	1660.118	16			

Discussion: One way ANOVA was applied to find whether there is significant difference among the educational setups in the academic skill development of boys with intellectually disabled. The ANOVA result shows that the calculated F-ratio value is 1.242 which is less than the table value of 3.739 at 5% level of significance. Since the calculated value is less than the table value it is inferred that there is no significant difference among the educational setup in academic skill development of boys with intellectually disabled. Hence the hypothesis is retained.

Ho2: There is no significant difference among the educational setups in the academic skill development of girls with intellectually disabled.

Table 2: Anova Test for Comparing Educational Setups in the Academic Skills Development of the Subject of the Girls Sample

Different Setups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Special School	4	27.5000	7.7244
Integrated School	4	33.0000	2.1602
Inclusive School	5	29.6000	3.9115
Total	13	30.0000	5.1316

ANOVA for Able to do Score

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	61.800	2	30.900	1.216	Ns
Within Groups	254.200	10	25.420		
Total	316.000	12			

Discussion: One way ANOVA was applied to find whether there is significant difference among the educational setups in the academic skill development of girls with intellectually disabled. The ANOVA result shows that the calculated F-ratio value is 2.216 which is less than the table value of 4.103 at 5% level of significance. Since the calculated value is less than the table value it is inferred that there is no significant difference among the educational setups in academic skill development of girls with intellectually disabled. Hence the hypothesis is retained.

Ho3: There is no significant difference in the academic skill development of boys and girls with intellectually disabled in difference educational setups.

Table 3: T-Test Comparison between Special and Inclusive Schools in the Academic Skill Development of the Sample

Sample	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Boys	17	26.4118	10.1861
Girls	13	30.0000	5.1316

T-test for Equality of Means

t	df	Sig.
1.1229	28	Ns

Discussion: The t-test was applied to find whether there is significant difference in the academic skill development of boys and girls with intellectually disabled in difference educational setups. The calculated t-test value is 1.1229 which is greater than the table value of 2.05 at 5% level of significance. Since the calculated value is greater than the table value it is inferred that there is significant difference in the academic skill development of boys and girls with intellectually disabled in difference educational setups. Hence the hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion

All the educational setup is equally effective for learning and acquiring knowledge for both girls and boys but due to some internal or external factors may not able to meet the need. The main purpose of the investigator is to find out the better educational setups in academic skill development of children with intellectual disability. It is evident from the above research studies that there is no much difference in educational setups for children with intellectual disabilities. From table 1 & 2, our research also shows that integrated school is providing better educational setups in present situation to both boys and girls. Also the mean of third table shows that the girls student is more scored academic skills development compare to boys student studied in different education setups. Inclusive education will become best educational setups after modifying the inclusive school concept. There is a great need of collaboration among the parents, teachers, administrators and policy makers to make more effective teaching and learning. Further researcher may also select different areas such as personal, social, recreational etc. apart from academics areas alone. The size of the sample shall be increased for more generalization of the study. The teacher should improve teaching strategies for better learning for the children with intellectual disability.

References

1. Brahm (2008), Special Schools: What future for special schools and inclusion? Conceptual and professional perspectives, *British Journal of Special Education*, Vol. 35, Issue-3, pp. 136-143.
2. Conrad Carlberg & Kenneth Kavale (1980), The Efficacy of Special Versus Regular Class Placement for Exceptional Children: a Meta-Analysis, *The Journal of Special Education*, Vol. 14, No. 3, pp. 295-309.
3. Florian, Lani (2008), Special or Inclusive Education: Future Trends, *British Journal of Special Education*, Vol. 35, No. 4, pp. 202-208.
4. Mani MNG & Manivannan M. (2004), Educational programs for children with learning disabilities. *Edutracks*, Vol. 4, pp. 31-33.
5. Nugent, Mary (2007), Support for Learning, *British Journal of Special Education*, Vol. 22, pp. 52-59.
6. Punani B. (1997), Comparative evaluation of the effectiveness of various modes of education of visually impaired children, *Disabilities and Impairments*, Vol. 11(2), pp. 86-102.
7. Yadava, S. (2013), Inclusive Education: Challenges and Prospects in India, *Educationia Confab*, Vol. 2, No. 4, pp. 39-46.